

Accelerated Neural Enhancement for Video Analytics with Video Quality Adaptation

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Abstract—The quality of the video stream is the key to neural network-based video analytics. However, low-quality video is inevitably collected by existing surveillance systems because of poor-quality cameras or over-compressed/pruned video streaming protocols, *e.g.*, as a result of upstream bandwidth limit. To address this issue, existing studies use quality enhancers (*e.g.*, neural super-resolution) to improve the quality of videos (*e.g.*, resolution) and eventually ensure inference accuracy. Nevertheless, directly applying quality enhancers does not work in practice because it will introduce unacceptable latency. In this paper, we present AccDecoder, a novel accelerated decoder for real-time and neural-enhanced video analytics, selects a few frames adaptively via Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to enhance the quality and inference then reuse on the unselected ones. Next, we extend AccDecoder to AccDecoder+ by formulating the resolution-involved Markov decision process (MDP) to achieve resolution adaptation; it aims to trade accuracy and latency corresponding under various video resolutions. Proved by experiments, AccDecoder provides efficient inference capability via filtering important frames using DRL for DNN-based inference and reusing the results for the other frames via extracting the reference relationship among frames and blocks, which contributes 6-21% accuracy improvement and a latency reduction of 20-80% than baselines. Compared with AccDecoder, AccDecoder+ achieves an additional 2-7% accuracy improvement.

Index Terms—Video analytics, super-resolution, deep reinforcement learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The advances in computer vision offer tremendous opportunities for autonomous analytics of videos generated by pervasive video cameras. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) [1]–[4] have been developed to dramatically improve the accuracy for various vision tasks while introducing stringent demands on computational resources. Due to the compute-resource shortage of commercial cameras, videos often stream to powerful servers for inference, resulting in the distributed video analytics pipeline (VAP) [5], [6].

Nevertheless, providing accurate video analytics remains challenging for state-of-the-art distributed VAPs. Since most VAPs currently rely on high-resolution video, such as for object detection, providing high accuracy when analyzing low-quality video is a challenge. For example, the accuracy of

Faster R-CNN [3], a modern DNN-based inference method, can only achieve around 56% accuracy for videos in 360p and 61% accuracy for videos in 540p which are collected by [7]. However, low-quality videos are inevitably collected by existing surveillance systems. One of the reasons is that existing low-quality collectors can only capture low-resolution frames. For example, New York city’s department of transportation [8] has made videos from all 752 traffic cameras for the public; however, the videos are transmitted at an extremely low resolution (240p) due to the default configuration of cameras [9]. Another reason is that current video streaming protocols over-compress/prune videos due to upstream bandwidth limitations. For example, AWSstream [10] aggressively reduces the resolution of the video from 540p to 360p and the frame rate from 1 to 0.83. It eventually brings about a 66% saving of bandwidth with a reduced accuracy from 61% to 54%.

To address this challenge, some VAPs [11], [12] try to utilize image enhancement models like Super Resolution (SR) [2], [13] and Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [14] to enhance images before feeding them into the inference model. This idea is inspired by the observation from the computer vision community – running object recognition-related tasks on high-resolution images can significantly improve detection accuracy [13]. However, image enhancement introduces extra latency, resulting in around 500 ms end-to-end latency [15], which is far from the real-time requirement (*e.g.*, less than 15-30 ms for real-time object recognition [6]).

Although DNN-aware video enhancement provides a promising way to improve inference accuracy [16], there is still much room for improvement. First, prior image enhancement mechanisms are rarely aware to video contents. They treat each received frame equally, but not all the frames deserve to be enhanced. For example, only the frames containing vehicles are valuable for traffic flow analysis; on the contrary, enhancing frames with empty streets is worthless but only increases system latency. Therefore, content-agnostic enhancement mechanisms cannot avoid being suboptimal. Second, although new DNN frameworks are designed to accurately recognize important frames (*e.g.*, [17], [18]), they are too heavy to achieve low latency. Third, decoding all the frames for analytics is computationally intensive and time-consuming, and video encoding contains plenty of unexploited but handy information, such as motion vectors (MVs) and residuals, to capture the important frames. We argue that the codec

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information, though inaccurate, is valuable enough to reveal important content, thereby speeding up video analytics.

Motivated by the above insights, we present AccDecoder, a novel accelerated video streaming decoder for real-time and neural-enhanced video analytics. AccDecoder is a content-aware DNN-integrated video decoder utilizing codec information to select a few frames, called *anchor frames*, for quality enhancement, and some frames, called *inference frames*, for DNN-aware inference. In particular, AccDecoder applies SR to anchor frames and transfers the quality-enhanced content to benefit the entire video according to the frame reference relationships; it further leverages codec information to reuse the results of inference frames for acceleration.

Challenge and solution. AccDecoder needs to adapt to various quality of videos to enable robust and real-time video analytics. Since SR and DNN-based inference is time-consuming, an accuracy-latency tradeoff must be made carefully to keep low latency without drastically compromising the accuracy. Our preliminary study (see more in Sec. II and III) shows that AccDecoder needs adaptive metrics for anchor and inference frame selection according to factors like video content and quality. In other words, various videos (or even different chunks of the same video) demand different settings for frame selection, but a static setting is not adaptive to the varying contents of videos. To address this issue, we leverage powerful and wide-used deep reinforcement learning (DRL) [19]–[21] to solve these dynamic and sequential problems [22], [23]. Specifically, AccDecoder enables adaptive settings via DRL in frame selection to accelerate video analytics and achieve a good tradeoff between accuracy and latency.

Our contributions are summarized as follows.

- We design a novel content-aware DNN integrated video decoder that is resilient and robust to the quality of videos. For example, for a 540p crossroad video collected by [7], AccDecoder can improve 10-38% accuracy compared with the state-of-the-art VAPs (see Fig. 2).
- We exploit temporal redundancies within a video and codec information to drastically increase the speed of analytics. For example, AccDecoder performs 1.5-8.0 times faster compared with AStream [10], DDS [5], and Glimpse [24] (see Fig. 2).
- Designed as a portable decoder, AccDecoder can easily work with any streaming-aware VAPs (*e.g.*, Reducto [6]). Plugging AccDecoder in them can obtain 6-21% accuracy improvement without compromising much speed and even get 3 – 7 \times speed up for some VAPs (see Fig. 3).
- We upgrade AccDecoder to AccDecoder+, significantly improving its generality and scalability. This enhancement now enables AccDecoder+ to seamlessly work with a diverse array of heterogeneous cameras, including those with varying resolutions and adaptive encoders that dynamically adjust resolution (such as AStream [10], Pensieve [25], and Chameleon [26]). Upgrading to AccDecoder+ can achieve 2% to 7% accuracy improvement (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 1: Distributed video analytics pipeline.

- We conducted a thorough examination of the scalability of AccDecoder+, developed a prototype and conducted experiments in a multi-stream environment (see Fig. 24).

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. We first present the background and motivation in Sec. II. Then we discuss AccDecoder and AccDecoder+'s key design in Sec. III, followed by our implementation in Sec. IV. The experimental studies are demonstrated in Sec. V. In Sec. VI, we introduce some related work, and conclude this paper in Sec. VII.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

We introduce distributed VAPs and the video codec, followed by performance requirements of VAPs that drive our design (*i.e.*, high accuracy, low end-to-end latency, and low overheads). We then elaborate on why prior solutions struggle to meet the three requirements simultaneously.

A. Background

Distributed Video Analytics. The proliferation of video analytics is facilitated by the advances of deep learning and the low prices of high-resolution network-connected cameras. However, the accuracy improvement from deep learning comes at a high computational cost. Although state-of-the-art smart cameras can support deep learning methods, the current surveillance and traffic cameras show only suboptimal use of resources. For example, DNNCam [27] which ships with a high-end embedded NVIDIA TX2 GPU [28] costs more than \$2000 while the price of deployed traffic cameras today ranges only from \$40 to \$200. These cameras are typically loaded with a single-core CPU, only providing scarce computing resources. Because of this huge gap, typical VAPs follow a distributed architecture. A typical distributed VAP architecture includes a filter and an encoder on the camera side and a decoder and an inference model on the server side, as illustrated in Fig. 1. In live analytics, video frames are continuously encoded and sent to a remote server that runs the inference DNN to analyze the video in an online fashion. For example, a vehicle detection pipeline consists of a front-end traffic camera (which compresses and streams live videos to a compute-powerful edge/cloud GPU server upon wire/wireless networks) and a back-end server (which decodes received video into frames and feeds them into inference models like Faster R-CNN [3] to detect vehicles). Such an architecture brings challenges in bandwidth cost, and thus some schemes rely on aggressively pruning videos (*via*, *e.g.*, reconfiguration, filtering) to meet upstream bandwidth limitations.

Fig. 2: AccDecoder vs. baselines.

Fig. 3: AccDecoder applied to pipelines.

Fig. 4: AccDecoder+ vs. AccDecoder.

Video codec is the key technology in distributed VAPs. It comprises an encoder and a decoder, a software/hardware program used to compress/decompress video files for efficient storage or network delivery. The encoder compresses video data and wraps them into mainstream video formats (*e.g.*, H.264 [29]), and the decoder decompresses the compressed video data into frames before post-processing (*e.g.*, playback or analysis).

This compression process is usually lossy, which strikes a balance between the video quality and the compression ratio according to the self-preference of codecs and encoding settings of users (*e.g.*, bitrate, frame rate, and group of pictures). We take H.264, one of the most popular codecs, as an example to explain the compression process. During encoding, each video frame is first divided into non-overlapped macroblocks (16×16 pixels), then to each macroblock, the encoder searches for the optimal compression method (including the block division types and encoding types of each block) according to the pixel-level similarity and encoding settings. One macroblock may be further divided into non-overlapped blocks (8×8 or 8×16 pixels) encoded with intra- or inter-frame types. The intra-coded block is encoded using the reference block with the most pixel-value similarity, and the offset between these two blocks is encoded into an MV with a residual. With the same procedure, the inter-coded block locates the most pixel-value similar block searched by the reference index and the MV from other frames. An MV indicates the spatial offset between the target block and its reference, while the difference in pixel values of two blocks is encoded as the residual for decoding. According to the encoding types, intra- or inter-frames are categorized into I- (intra-encoded), P- (only referred to historical frames), and B- (bi-referred to historical and future frames).

An ideal distributed VAP should meet three goals:

- **High accuracy.** Inspired by the success of image enhancement methods in video streaming for quality of experience (QoE) improvement [30]–[33], researchers try to use image enhancement for machine-centric video analytics [15], [33], [34]. For example, [15] leverages SR to enhance image details for robotics applications, while [33] embeds GAN on Google Glasses to generate facial features for face recognition. The experimental results from [15], [33] demonstrate that image enhancement improves inference accuracy.

- **Low latency.** The latency of decoding the video (*i.e.*, decoding latency), inference, and streaming the video to the server (*i.e.*, streaming latency) should be low. Previous works focus on reducing the size of streaming to reduce the streaming latency (*e.g.*, Reducto [3]), learning and filtering key frames for inference, and utilizing MVs to reuse the other frames.
- **Low bandwidth cost.** Bandwidth cost is defined as the total size of a video file delivered from the camera to the server of each VAP as its bandwidth cost. Given the limited ability of the network to transmit video from the camera to the server, bandwidth cost should be considered as a metric for evaluating VAP performance.

B. Motivation

Limitations of previous work. Although a couple of bandwidth-saving and accuracy-improvement approaches have been developed, three significant limitations remain.

- **Adaptive encoding in cameras.** A camera may leverage light-weight DNN [35] or heuristic methods (*e.g.*, inter-frame pixel-level difference [24]) to distinguish and prune frames/regions without labeled information. These methods, however, may cause false positives (*e.g.*, pixel-level change in the background may trigger the camera to send many frames) and false negatives (*e.g.*, light-weight object detection model may miss small appeared objects), thus increasing bandwidth cost or reducing the inference accuracy. Server-side decision-making controls the camera’s actions with feedback from the cloud. For example, according to the servers’ instruction, the camera in [5] iteratively delivers the region of interest in a higher resolution. The server-side decision-making introduces extra latency, especially due to the information delivery between the camera and the cloud crossing a wide area network.
- **Image enhancement in servers.** Image enhancement contributes to higher accuracy but yields higher latency (see Fig. 5). Recent studies, though, have successfully leveraged image enhancement to increase QoE and inference accuracy, they still suffer from high latency. This originates from the much heavier model structure of image enhancement than other discriminate tasks. For instance, the complexity of the SR model is 1000 times higher than image classification and object detection models in terms of MultAdds [12], as SR

outputs high-resolution (HR) images whereas others output labels or Bounding boxes (Bbox). In other words, naively enhancing all the frames is not practical in real-time video analytics applications.

Fig. 5: Comparing accuracy and latency with various schemes.

- Bi-pipeline video analytics.** The existing bi-pipeline methods reduce the time cost by analysis in two main ways. On the one hand, some bi-pipeline methods (*e.g.*, [32], [36]) apply SR on a subset of frames and transfer their gain to the remaining frames. It can reduce processing time compared with SR for all frames. Nevertheless, with a mean inference time hovering around 60 ms (refer to Fig. 5), the inference alone already surpasses the real-time analytics requirement of approximately 30 ms. The incorporation of SR leads to an additional extension of latency, surpassing the real-time analytics requirement, irrespective of the reduced quantity. On the other hand, certain bi-pipeline methods (*e.g.*, [24]) implement inference on a subset of frames and reuse the results to predict the outcomes of other frames, thereby reducing latency. However, reuse can introduce errors and result in reduced accuracy, as shown in Fig. 5. In summary, bi-pipeline schemes fail to achieve a satisfactory trade-off between latency and accuracy for real-time analysis tasks. Therefore, we advocate considering the incorporation of three pipelines (*i.e.*, SR, inference, and reuse) to enhance overall performance. This approach utilizes SR to improve accuracy and reuse to reduce latency.

Our preliminary study confirms the challenge in the tradeoff between accuracy and latency in video analytics, as shown in Fig. 5. Due to resource restrictions, to use existing techniques in real-time and provide high accuracy, servers need to adaptively shift multiple pipelines, including inference after SR using HR frames, inference with low-resolution frames (LR), and reuse the last inference results. However, conventional algorithms (*e.g.*, k-nearest neighbor (KNN) used in [6]) are largely suboptimal as they ignore the temporal relationship among frames and the possibility of transferring high-quality frames to the whole video. Therefore, we aim to design an efficient decoder to schedule the multiple pipelines for video analytics adaptively.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

This section first describes the design goals and overview of AccDecoder, then presents the challenges of achieving

these goals and the specific design choices to tackle these challenges.

A. Design Goals

We take a pragmatic stance to focus on the server-side decoder because most of the installed surveillance or traffic cameras only have cheap CPUs without programmable ability [6]; besides, rich information that may improve VAPs' performance in the decoder has not been excavated. In this context, we propose AccDecoder, a portable tool/decoder which can be plugged into any VAPs for video streaming analytics to achieve high accuracy, limited latency (*e.g.*, 30 ms), and low-resource goals simultaneously. As illustrated in Fig. 6, AccDecoder achieves these goals via the following three mechanisms: 1) Pipeline ① leverages SR model enhancing a small set of LR *anchor frames* to HR ones to achieve high accuracy. 2) Pipeline ② and Pipeline ③ extract the codec information (*e.g.*, frames reference relationship, MVs, and residuals), then utilize them to *transfer* the gains of enhanced anchor frames and *reuse* DNN inference results (*e.g.*, Bbox in object detection) onto the entire video respectively. *Transfer* and *reuse* amortize the computational overhead of SR and inference across the entire video and thus achieve low latency. 3) The *scheduler* classifies all frames into three subsets, and each executes one of three pipelines. It can greatly reduce latency and computational cost by exploiting the content features of the keyframes (*e.g.*, the intra-coded frame) and the change of codec information (*e.g.*, residuals of continuous frames). Furthermore, AccDecoder is upgraded to AccDecoder+, which has resolution awareness to support self-adaptation to video quality.

Fig. 6: Architecture of AccDecoder and AccDecoder+. Features of resolution are new for AccDecoder+.

B. System Model

Path towards the goal. We seek answers to the following pivotal questions, which lead to our key design choices. Q1 — How to effectively transfer the gains of SR to up-scale non-anchor frames? Q2 — How to reuse the results of inference to the other frames? Q3 — How to assign appropriate decoding pipelines to frames in a fine spatial granularity to achieve a better accuracy-latency tradeoff than baselines?

Q1 – How to transfer gains of SR to non-anchor frames?

Approach: Pipeline ① + ②. To make the best of reuse, AccDecoder enhances *anchor frames* with the SR model and caches the output (see ① in Fig. 7); then it transfers the enhancement benefit to non-anchor frames with the reference information and the cached outputs (see ② in Fig. 7). This approach follows the same findings in [2] and [32], where most of the latency of SR occurs at the last couple of layers. Namely, caching and reusing the final output (*i.e.*, high-resolution images) is most effective in achieving low latency.

Fig. 7: Process of SR gain transfer inspired by [32] and [29].

Fig. 7 illustrates the process of transferring SR gains to a non-anchored frame for the inter-coded type. Modern video codec encodes/decodes frames based on non-overlapped *inter-* and *intra-coded* blocks (§II-A). AccDecoder uses the reference index, MVs, and the residual in the codec information to decode a target block. The process is the same as the original decoding except for the additional SR, scaling, and interpolation modules (blue boxes in Fig. 7). First, AccDecoder selects the reference blocks among cached anchor frames following the inference index. Next, AccDecoder up-scales the MV with the same amplification factor as SR (*e.g.*, from 270p to 1080p is 4). Following the MV, AccDecoder transfers the SR gain from the reference block in the cached frame to the target one. In the end, AccDecoder up-scales the residual by light-weight interpolation (*e.g.*, bilinear or bicubic), accumulates it to the transferred block to output the HR block and pastes on the non-anchor frame. To the intra-coded blocks without the cached reference anchor frame, AccDecoder directly decodes and up-scales them by interpolation. Fortunately, with our carefully designed scheduler, most intra-coded blocks are assigned to the SR pipeline; the impact of the minority of interpolated intra-coded blocks can be negligible.

Difference from the state of the art. Two prior works also leverage frame dependency to accelerate SR, but they differ from this paper by the different scopes and different frame schedulers. NEMO [32] is well-studied in transferring SR gains to other frames; its scheduler adopts a greedy strategy to choose the anchor frame set that provides the most quality gain. However, the iterative method proves to be too slow for real-time analytics because NEMO, not originally designed for real-time tasks, overlooks this limitation. For acceleration, NeuroScaler [36] optimizes speed by modifying the scheduler, introducing an empirical preset threshold to filter frames and selectively enhancing those with accumulated

residual differences surpassing the set threshold. This approach can accelerate the frame selection but weakens the robustness of SR transfer, and cannot achieve a satisfactory trade-off of latency and accuracy in video analytic tasks. NeuroScaler, tailored for video playback tasks, excels in achieving real-time implementation for video playback. However, its effectiveness in delivering real-time performance for video analytics tasks is limited, falling significantly below the required speed threshold. Differing from them, in this paper, we leverage the learnability of DRL to speed up the selection and also guarantee accuracy.

Q2 – How to reuse inference results for non-inference frames?

Approach: Pipeline ③. AccDecoder infers *inference frames* using the inference model and caches the results; then, it uses the MVs and cached results to infer non-inference frames (see ③ in Fig. 6). MV indicates the offset between the target and reference blocks (§II-A). Here we use the object detection task as an example, which aims to identify objects (*i.e.*, their locations and classes) on each frame in videos. Fig. 8 reveals that the MVs between the last inference frame and the current frame can perfectly match the movement of objects’ Bboxes (*i.e.*, the results of object detection).

Fig. 8: Relation between MVs and Bboxes.

The *Reuse* module in Pipeline ③ gets the result of the last inference frame (dotted line in Fig. 6), calculates the mean of all MVs that reside in each Bbox, and uses it to shift each Bbox to the current position. MV, as the block-level offset, is hard to express any semantic meaning (*e.g.*, object moving) [37]. Our preliminary study implies that the accuracy of *reuse* degrades significantly after the MV, which spans multiple reference frames (*e.g.*, over 7-10 frames in [7], [38], [39]).

Optimization. AccDecoder uses two techniques to boost the accuracy of inference results reuse. First, it filters the noisy MVs caused by the camera shaking in the image background. These noisy MVs are often magnitude orders smaller than the common ones caused by moving objects, hence can be filtered with conventional statistical methods. According to the experiment results on dataset [38]–[40], we regard the MVs whose value is equal to zero or greater than the mean value plus 0.8 times the standard deviation in the Bbox as noise, then filter them. Second, to cope with the change in Bbox size due to the object’s movement, AccDecoder expands the MV calculation region to each direction by 16 pixels (*i.e.*, one more macroblock, motion vectors are calculated on

a per-macroblock basis). Note that the reuse module is not necessary to tackle but only remit this erosion because the *scheduler* module in (Q3) effectively controls it by judiciously distributing inference frames.

Progress beyond the state of the art. Some prior work (*e.g.*, [41]–[43]) leverages lightweight MV-based methods to reuse analytics results and thus speed up inference. As live streams are intentionally designed to exclude B-frames during video encoding in order to minimize coding time, the existing MV-based methods disregard B-frames. However, the H.264 and H.265 video encoding standards both incorporate B-frames to enhance video compression efficiency. To propose a universal decoder, we need to develop a new algorithm to implement MV-based reuse for videos, whether they include B-frames or not. Therefore, the proposed algorithm needs to account for bi-directional prediction frames, as B-frames can refer to historical and future frames. The rationale behind this lies in the fact that modern video codecs with B-frames prioritize minimizing video size, focusing solely on volume reduction without necessarily aligning with the playback order. Consequently, the coding order diverges significantly from the playback order. Thus, the reference blocks used to calculate the target block’s MV can be distributed throughout the video. In other words, the target block may even refer to future frames in the playback order, a scenario referred to as backward reference. Furthermore, the reuse algorithm in AccDecoder is designed to operate in the compressed video space, enabling accelerated bi-directional prediction, instead of calculating MV between consecutive frames as in previous works. Specifically, we build a mapping relation that maps the coding order to the playback order using POC (*Pic_Order_Cnt*) in the compressed video [44]. Our reuse algorithm relies on two important observations. Firstly, a frame can reference multiple frames within codecs, but the primary referred frame is the one closest in playback order. Hence, we can utilize the primary referred frame for prediction to simplify the process. Secondly, the frame f_t (excluding I-frames) either forward references frame f_{t-1} or is backward referenced by frame f_{t-1} , where t is the index in the playback order. Based on the above observations, our reuse algorithm can be outlined as follows: (1) When the current frame f_t is an I-frame, the results of its previous frame f_{t-1} are reused without prediction, as I-frames do not have MV. (2) B- and P-frames undergo the same processing, where the main idea is to identify dependencies with the previous frame. If the current frame f_t forward references the previous frame f_{t-1} in playback order, we use the forward MVs of the current frame f_t to predict the movement of bounding boxes. Alternatively, if the current frame f_t is backward referenced by the previous frame f_{t-1} in playback order, we utilize the backward MVs of the previous frame f_{t-1} for predicting results.

Q3 — How to guarantee accuracy-latency balance with adaptation for different quality of video?

Approach: Scheduler. The key to the accuracy-latency trade-off is how to optimally assign decoding pipelines (*i.e.*, SR,

inference, and reuse) to frames in fine spatial granularity. As analyzed in Fig. 5, different pipelines for frame decoding and analytics lead to different levels of accuracy and latency. ❶ For each frame in an SR class, selected anchor frames are enhanced by the SR model; after this, the scheduler feeds the up-scaling frame into the inference DNN for inference (*e.g.*, object detection). ❷ The frames in the inference class enjoy the benefits from the SR frames following the references in Fig. 7, and then are fed into the inference DNN model for inference. Their accuracy still increases due to the benefits transferred from the SR frames. Note that the transfer is quite fast (the time cost is the same as normal frame decoding) as it only includes additional bicubic interpolation on residual per frame compared to normal frame decoding. ❸ For those frames in the reuse class, *e.g.*, object detection, we get the Bbox of each object in the last (playback order) detected frame, calculate the mean of all MVs that reside in the Bbox, and use it to shift the previous position to the current position.

Model for pipeline selection. We formulate the adaptive pipeline selection problem to maximize the accuracy under the latency constraint. Given a video containing the set of frames F , one of the three pipelines is selected for each frame, which can be expressed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{argmax}_{\mathbf{x}} \quad & \frac{1}{|F|} \sum_{f \in F} \operatorname{Acc}_f(x_f) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{f \in F} \operatorname{Latency}_f(x_f) \leq \tau, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, \dots, x_F\}$ is the selection set and $x_f \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ is for pipeline selection, Acc_f is the accuracy of a frame, $\operatorname{Latency}_f$ is the latency of a frame given the selected pipeline, and τ is latency tolerant for a set of frames F .

Fig. 9: Frame vs. residual in correlations between the difference values and the changes of Bboxes, and time cost in feature extraction.

Finding the optimal pipeline selection is tricky due to the large searching space $3^{|F|}$. We are inspired by Reducto [6] which adaptively filters frame via setting a threshold on frame differencing. Thus, we introduce two thresholds tr_1 and tr_2

on frame differencing to cluster frames into three pipelines:

$$x_f := I_f(tr_1, tr_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } D(f, f_I) \geq tr_1 \\ & \text{and } D(f, f_S) \geq tr_2, \\ 2, & \text{if } D(f, f_I) \geq tr_1 \\ & \text{and } D(f, f_S) < tr_2, \\ 3, & \text{others,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where f_S and f_I respectively represent the last SR frame and the last inferred frame of frame f , and D quantifies the disparity in edge features between these two frames. When the frame difference is greater than tr_2 , the frame will enter pipeline ①, and otherwise, if it is only greater than tr_1 it will enter pipeline ②. The constraint of real-time video analytics (e.g., speed of analytics ≥ 30 fps) restricts us from extracting the light-weighted features to categorize frames. Different from [6], we find out the Laplacian (i.e., edge features) on the residual and the frames have a high correlation with the inference accuracy (see Fig. 9(a)). At the same time, executing the Laplacian operator on the residual can save 34% time than that on frame (see Fig. 9(b)). One intuitive reason is that information on residuals is sparse and de-redundant. It preserves differences among frames but is not too dense to process, thus providing a good opportunity to categorize frames efficiently.

Fig. 10: Best thresholds vary across videos.

Solution. Categorizing frames into three classes for pipelines is not trivial. Across various videos, their best threshold combination differs (as shown in Fig. 10). Furthermore, the optimal thresholds for frame feature differences (e.g., pixel and residual differences) among chunks in one video vary greatly. Fig. 11 plots the best thresholds on the videos in [38], which implies we should dynamically adjust the threshold for each chunk. Therefore, the scheduler needs to offer adaptive threshold settings.

To adaptively set the thresholds, we formulate this problem as a Markov decision process (MDP) where the scheduler in AccDecoder learns to set proper thresholds for each chunk. The MDP is a discrete-time stochastic process, which can be defined by a quad-tuple $\langle s, a, r, p \rangle$. In this tuple, s is the set of states, a is the set of actions, r is the set of rewards, and p is the probability of transition from state s_t to next state s_{t+1} based on action a_t . While processing frames, the scheduler’s goal is to cluster them into three pipelines (i.e., a)

Fig. 11: Best thresholds vary across chunks (even adjacent).

such that the expected long-run reward $\mathbb{E}[R] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k}$ is maximum, where $\gamma \in (0, 1]$ is a discount factor for future rewards to dampen the effect of future rewards on the action. We define how the MDP is parameterized as follows (see Fig. 12).

Fig. 12: DRL-based scheduler designed in AccDecoder and AccDecoder+.

- **State:** The state of AccDecoder consists of two components: (1) the content info of the video chunk representative by the semantic feature of key frames and (2) the difference among continuous frames (X_1, \dots, X_n) in one chunk extracted by the fast Laplacian operator. To extract the content features of the key frame (i.e., the first frame of the current chunk), a $1 \times 1 \times 1000$ fully connected FC-1000 layer of VGG16 is performed first, [45]; then, concatenates a principal component analysis (PCA) module compressing the output to 128 dimensions. For the difference among frames, we calculate the inter-frame distance between every two continuous frames of each chunk; in particular, apply a Laplacian operator on each frame’s residual (i.e., the difference of content boundaries) and then calculate their distance as discussed in Sec.III-B. We also consider the continuity between chunks, it is also necessary to add information about inter-chunk, that is, the difference of edge features between the key frame and the last inference frame in the previous chunk.

AccDecoder+ brings in additional information in the state, i.e., resolution, to adapt the scheduling to coping the various resolution of video streams. The reason is that the resolution is a critical factor that caused the most fluctuating accuracy and latency in video analytics. From our preliminary study, we find that it takes more time to upscale a high-resolution video via SR due to the large number of pixels that need to be processed. For example, 270p and 540p videos are upscaled by SR by $2 \times$ at a cost of 74ms and 220ms respectively, showing a $3 \times$ difference. However, in practice, the server commonly receives videos with various resolutions

(e.g., from different cameras or by adaptive encoding) for analytics. Therefore, we design AccDecoder+ by taking video quality into account, which is chunks' resolution.

- **Action:** The action is to set two thresholds, $a_t = (tr_1, tr_2)$, for each chunk. tr_1 selects the frame set F_1 feeding into the inference model from all frames in one chunk, and tr_2 further chooses frames F_2 from F_1 for enhancement. The rest frames in this chunk reuse the inference results with the frame dependency info in the video decoder. Sequentially selecting frame sets F_1 and F_2 instead of in parallel because (1) the sequential way greatly decreases the search space and lowers the training difficulty of DRL by using smaller action space; (2) the frames in each set selected by such two ways maybe not be identical while the inference accuracy is similar (the accuracy distance between them no more than 0.5% in the experimental datasets).

The action for threshold selection is normalized as $tr_1 \in [0, 1]$, $tr_2 \in [0, 3]$. It is challenging to make accurate decisions for a large space of actions [46]. Therefore, we discretize the action space to reduce the exploration space by n-equal fractions. Next, we explore how to set the fractions n_1 and n_2 for tr_1 and tr_2 properly. We find that the performance does not keep improving with the fine-granularity level of thresholds (i.e., n increasing), especially for tr_2 (see Fig. 13¹). Therefore, we choose coarse granularity to minimize the action space, i.e., $n_1 = 15$ and $n_2 = 5$. The range of these two thresholds is set according to expert knowledge, therefore, we finally set action space as $tr_1 \in \{0.05, 0.10, 0.15, \dots, 0.75\}$ and $tr_2 \in \{0.5, 1.0, \dots, 2.5\}$. All possible combinations of tr_1 and tr_2 are defined as Tr , excluding cases where tr_2 is less than tr_1 .

(a) 3D plotting with n_1 and n_2 (b) Accuracy vs. complexity

Fig. 13: The changes generated in the optimal accuracy within latency tolerance as the complexity of the action space rises.

- **Reward:** Given that AccDecoder aims to maximize the inference accuracy within a tolerable latency. Therefore, the reward is designed to include two aspects, namely, the average accuracy of the chunk and the latency required to obtain the inference results for the chunk. Our goal is to achieve real-time inference, so the chunk needs to be analyzed before the arrival of the next chunk (e.g., within 1s

¹This figure is obtained by training the model in the enumerated possibility space using a small dataset [38]–[40].

for each chunk); otherwise, there is a penalty for exceeding the specified time. Therefore, the reward for each chunk t is defined as follows.

$$r_t = \frac{\alpha_1}{|F_t|} \sum_{f \in F_t} Acc_f(x_f) - \alpha_2 P_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2}), \quad (3)$$

where α_1 and α_2 are the weight factors to balance the preference for latency and accuracy. Here, x_f is the pipeline selection for frame f using the two thresholds, see Eq. (2). The value of α in reward can be adjusted based on different service preferences and requirements. P_t is a penalty function of chunk t for latency exceeding the tolerance τ .

$$P_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } Latency_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2}) > \tau, \\ 0, & \text{others.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $Latency_t$ represents the analytics latency of chunk t . It is the cumulative latency of frames in chunk F_t , and can be calculated as $Latency_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2}) = \sum_{f \in F_t} Latency_f(x_f)$.

The process of DRL in frame selection is shown below. At each chunk t , the agent observes the current state s_t and gives an action a_t according to its policy. Then, the environment returns reward r_t as feedback, and moves to the next state s_{t+1} according to the transition probability $P(s_{t+1}|s_t, a_t)$. The goal to find an optimal policy can thus be formulated as the mathematical problem of maximizing the expectation of cumulative discounted return $R_t = \sum_{k=t}^T \gamma^{k-t} r_k$, where $\gamma \in (0, 1]$ is a discount factor for future rewards to dampen the effect of future rewards on the action; r_k is the reward of each step, and T is the number of chunks in the video.

Fig. 14: The scheduler (agent) training with A3C.

Model Training. Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C) [47] is used to train the DRL-based scheduler in AccDecoder and AccDecoder+ (see Fig. 14). The reason behind the algorithm selection is that A3C can improve learning efficiency, as it consists of multiple independent agents that can interact with environments in parallel including data collection and training. The process of learning is (1) Each agent interacts with the environment to obtain samples (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) and executes the actor-critic algorithm and gradient descent independently. In each agent, the critic learns the value function $V^\pi(s_t; \theta_v)$ while the actor learns a policy $\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t; \theta_a)$ in parallel. (2) The gradients of agents are asynchronously sent to a central parameter server to update. Next,

the central parameter server integrates the received gradients to generate a global model. (3) The central parameter server then pushes the new model to each agent and starts the next round of training until the central agent’s actor model converges. Finally, the agents are asynchronously synchronized with the global model.

In the following, we give details about how to train models in agents locally.

Critics: The state-value under policy π is defined as the expected cumulative reward $V^\pi(s; \theta_v) = \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s)}[Q(s, a)|s_t = s]$ following policy π from state s . The critic networks are trained to estimate values $V^\pi(s; \theta_v)$ following:

$$\theta_v \leftarrow \theta_v - \lambda_c \sum_t \nabla_{\theta_v} [r_t + \gamma V^\pi(s_{t+1}; \theta_v) - V^\pi(s_t; \theta_v)]^2, \quad (5)$$

where λ_c is the learning rate of the critics.

Actors: The actors learn a policy $\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t; \theta_a)$ by updating their parameters θ_a to follow

$$\theta_a \leftarrow \theta_a + \lambda_a \sum_t \nabla_{\theta_a} \log \pi(s_t, a_t) A(s_t, a_t), \quad (6)$$

where λ_a is the learning rate of actors and $A(s_t, a_t)$ is an estimate of the advantage function represented as

$$A(s_t, a_t) = r_t + \gamma V^\pi(s_{t+1}; \theta_v) - V^\pi(s_t; \theta_v). \quad (7)$$

Intuitively, the advantage function implies how better it is to take a specific action compared to the average and general action given state s_t . Furthermore, to encourage agent exploration, an entropy regularisation term is introduced to the actor’s updates. Meanwhile, augmenting the objective function with a regularization term promotes the discovery of distributions with higher entropy, so that they are less likely to converge to a particular action during training. Thus, Eq. (6) is changed as follows.

$$\Delta \theta_a = \lambda_a \sum_t \nabla_{\theta_a} \log \pi(s_t, a_t) A(s_t, a_t) + \beta \nabla_{\theta_a} H(\pi(\cdot|s_t)),$$

where $H(\cdot)$ is the policy entropy and β is the entropy weight.

Computational complexity. Firstly, in the scheduler, the searching space of the optimal pipeline selection is $\mathcal{O}(3^k)$, where k is the number of frames in a chunk. The searching space of AccDecoder/AccDecoder+’s scheduler is $\mathcal{O}(|a|)$, where $|a|$ is the number of possible actions. As we discretize the action space, therefore, the complexity of AccDecoder is much less than that of optimal pipeline selection. Secondly, we analyze the complexity of the DNN-based online execution in AccDecoder and AccDecoder+. The asymptotic complexity of AccDecoder/AccDecoder+ is $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{O}(F + C_0 + k_1 C_1 + (k_1 + k_2) C_2 + k_3 C_3)$, where k_i is the number of frames chosen pipeline i . The complexity $\mathcal{O}(F)$ represents the time required to obtain the feature map for each chunk, encompassing VGG16, PCA, and edge feature extraction. Notably, VGG and PCA only need to be executed for the first frame of each chunk. Hence, despite VGG’s relatively high complexity resulting from the substantial number of layers, its average complexity across the entire chunk with 30

frames remains within acceptable limits. $\mathcal{O}(C_0)$ denote the complexity of action-making in DRL for each chunk, and the complexity of each pipeline is $\mathcal{O}(C_1)$ for SR, $\mathcal{O}(C_2)$ for inference, and $\mathcal{O}(C_3)$ for reuse. Given F , C_0 and C_3 is much less than the complexity of C_1 and C_2 . Therefore, $\mathcal{A} \approx \mathcal{O}(k_1 C_1 + (k_1 + k_2) C_2)$, and the complexity depends on the scheduler’s decision: more anchor frames (*i.e.*, higher k_1) lead to higher complexity, and conversely, more reuse frames (*i.e.*, higher k_3) decrease the computational complexity.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the following discussion, we will address two crucial aspects concerning AccDecoder and AccDecoder+: their scalability and applicability.

Scalability. Both AccDecoder and AccDecoder+ can support scalability in a multi-stream environment by incorporating a resource allocation component within the server. Assuming multiple streams access a server, it is essential to appropriately allocate computing resources (*e.g.*, using time-slice allocation) to support their analytics. AccDecoder and AccDecoder+ adopt a time-slice scheme based on the distance of edge features among continuous frames (*i.e.*, a part of states mentioned in Sec. III). The rationale behind this approach is that the greater differences between frames indicate the more frames to undergo SR or inference, which, in turn, necessitates additional GPU slicing. The time-slicing for streams is designed to adhere to the ratio formulated as follows: $G_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n X_{ij}}{\sum_{k=0}^N \sum_{j=1}^n X_{kj}}$, where N is the number of streams and X_{ij} is the distance of edge feature between j -th and $j+1$ -th frame in stream i . On the other hand, CPU allocation also impacts the pipeline selection. Therefore, incorporating G_i into the states of the DRL agent enables it to make pipeline assignments based on available resources. Correspondingly, we modify the $P_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2})$ in reward function r_t of agent based on G_i as follows.

$$P_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } Latency_t(tr_{t,1}, tr_{t,2}) > \tau G_i, \\ 0, & \text{others.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Scope of AccDecoder+ vs. AccDecoder. Compared with AccDecoder, AccDecoder+ demonstrates better generality and scalability, enabling support for heterogeneous cameras. The capability to handle videos and video chunks in various resolutions is crucial, as it is a common occurrence in modern video analyzers. On the one hand, modern cameras can generate video chunks in different resolutions because they can achieve self-adaptive encoding by dynamically adjusting resolutions to accommodate network fluctuations and object size, as demonstrated in [25], [26]. On the other hand, the video analyzer can receive multiple video streams from different sources in different resolutions. AccDecoder is not designed to accommodate variable resolutions, leading to suboptimal processing performance for videos with varying resolutions. To achieve generality across different resolutions and reduce

the frequency of retraining edges to meet variable resolutions, we upgrade AccDecoder to AccDecoder+. Specifically, by importing resolution into the state of DRL, the agent can learn the optimal choices for chunks in different resolutions. Additional details and experimental comparisons are provided in Sec. VI.

There might be a misconception that AccDecoder+ is universally superior to AccDecoder. However, in the following discussion, we aim to clarify that each of them possesses unique advantages and is well-suited for specific scenarios. AccDecoder+ outperforms AccDecoder in heterogeneous scenarios with streams of various resolutions. This is because AccDecoder+ can achieve better generalization for various resolution streams by taking into account the influence of video resolutions. However, this comes at the cost of requiring larger training datasets and higher training costs. On the contrary, AccDecoder is specifically optimized to handle scenarios with homogeneous streams having the same resolution. As a result, AccDecoder requires a smaller training set, incurs lower training costs, and demonstrates higher accuracy for streams of a specific resolution. Both heterogeneous and homogeneous scenarios are quite common, making both methods valuable and relevant in their respective contexts.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

We implement AccDecoder as an intelligent decoder in both simulation and prototype. We first introduce the system settings of the experiment and the setup of the dataset and the baselines. Next, we introduce the training setup of AccDecoder on neural networks of DRL, SR, and DNN-based inference.²

A. System Settings, Dataset, and Baselines

System settings. The server component runs on an Ubuntu 18.04 instance with Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6226R CPU at 2.90GHz and 1 NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070 GPU. AccDecoder is built on H.264 codec [48], JM 19.0 version open source code [49], with 2470 LoC changes. In practice, there are several video codecs besides H.264, but they have a high similarity. For example, they share the same abstracts (*i.e.*, reference index, MV, and residual), which are essential information to transfer neural super-resolution outputs to non-anchor frames. Their difference is in low-level compression algorithms (*e.g.*, the number of reference frames and the size of blocks). Thus, while we only use H.264 to validate AccDecoder’s design, we believe the design is generic enough to accommodate different codecs.

Dataset. Our video dataset mainly contains public data streams from real-time surveillance cameras deployed worldwide. We collected video clips of different scenes and times from different camera data sources. Thus, video datasets with different properties (*e.g.*, time, illumination, vehicle and pedestrian density, road type, and direction) are obtained. All of our videos are available by searching on YouTube [38], [40], [50] and Yoda [7], [39], [51]. The videos are in 30fps, of which each chunk includes 30 frames.

Baselines. We compare AccDecoder’s performance with the following four baselines: (1) Glimpse [24] filters frames by comparing pixel-level frame differences against a static threshold. (2) AWStream [10] adapts encoding parameters (*i.e.*, quantization parameter (QP), resolution, and frame rate) of the underlying codec to cope with different available bandwidth; (3) DDS [5] applies different quality encodings to different regions via region proposal network (RPN) [3], which can offer trade-off accuracy and latency. (4) Reducto [6] filters unnecessary frames in its encoder via a dynamic setting threshold given by the server to save bandwidth in uploading. To avoid the influence of SR model itself but concentrate on VAPs, the ground truth in this paper is generated by Faster R-CNN with Resnet50 detecting each frame in 1080p video enhanced by EDSR from 540p.

B. DNN Implementation

DRL settings. In the experiments, we set $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 0.5$, and $\tau = 1s$ for each chunk according to our practical experience and requirements of services. We used A3C for training, including 16 agents, to obtain more experience and enhance the exploration and training speed. We use an Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 (*i.e.*, λ_a and λ_c). The discount factor for reward γ is 0.9. The initial value of the entropy weight β is 0.001, and the value will diminish with learning, allowing more opportunities to explore the space to increase rewards. Under our consideration, latency cost by DRL-based scheduler should not take up a major part thus a light-weight model is more appropriate. Therefore, we implement actor and critic networks in DRL as two-layer MLPs with 128 units and using ReLU as activation functions. The capacity of the replay buffer is 10^5 , and we take a minibatch of 256 to update the parameters of the neural networks. Considering that the computational cost of the SR model in multiple parallelized environments is too expensive. In order to minimize computation costs, all frames in datasets are fed into SR models and executed once. And we save the results and record the execution time for training.

Task-driven SR model. For object detection, we train the detection-driven SR model based on EDSR [52] following the analytics aware loss function [15] (*i.e.*, a weighted addition of visual quality loss and object detection inference loss). We use VisDrone [53] as the training set to train our model; use the testing set from VisDrone, video set from DDS [5] and Reducto [6] to evaluate its performance. The visual quality loss comes from the pair of original and downsampling frames; the object detection inference loss comes from the results of YOLOv4 [1] detecting on reconstructed frames (from the down sampling frames) and the labels. The initial weights of EDSR and YOLOv4 are provided by authoritative implementations [1], [54]. The weights of EDSR are updated during our training, but the one of YOLOv4 keeps static.

Inference DNN settings. We mainly evaluate AccDecoder’s performance on object detection. Here, we list the different DNNs used by AccDecoder for object detection. We choose two object detection models with different architectures in-

²Our prototype is available at <https://github.com/mi150/AccDecoder>.

Fig. 18: Comparing AccDe- coder with the scheme of SR all I-frames.

Fig. 19: Accuracy breakdown among components.

I-frames should be assigned to pipeline ① since they contain the most information, yielding the greatest contribution when enhanced via SR. To understand the underlying reasons, we conduct an exploration by comparing the approach that pre-assigns all I-frames to pipeline ① and uses the two thresholds to cluster other frames into pipelines ①, ②, and ③. We find that AccDecoder still exhibits a 3% accuracy improvement compared with the scheme of SR all I-frames, as shown in Fig. 18. I-frames, despite containing substantial information and being referenceable by other frames, are not the main features prioritized for SR. Conversely, the edge feature differences have been proven crucial for effective SR enhancement. AccDecoder can identify certain B- and P-frames that offer more gains in accuracy improvement compared with I-frames, particularly those with significant differences in edge features (*i.e.*, featuring new objects or distinctive characteristics). This capability contributes to AccDecoder’s superior performance even with only 12.7% of I-frames undergoing SR. In other words, pipeline assignment in AccDecoder is based on the extracted semantic-level information while frame type assignment in video codec by pixel-level; this gap means that there is no explicit relationship between frame type and the pipeline of frames. Fig. 17 depicts the result in one example chunk.

B. Component-wise Analysis

Performance breakdown. We break down the accuracy and the latency to illustrate the performance of each pipeline. As shown in Fig. 19, all three pipelines provide accuracy improvement. Without the SR pipeline, it drops 12% accuracy compared with the entire AccDecoder, while the impact of w/ or w/o transfer pipeline is relatively small (*i.e.*, around 5%). Transfer pipeline aims to improve the accuracy by detecting the objects in the enhanced frames which are blurred in the original ones. However, these objects usually make up a small fraction of traffic video. When opening up the DRL-based scheduler, frames assigned to the transfer pipeline only exist in a few chunks. Another fact is that transferring benefits from SR frames offers less improvement on small objects than on large or medium objects. It is because the blurred pixels caused by interpolation in small objects occupy a more considerable portion. Fig. 20 plots the latency breakdown for videos with 270p, 360p, and 540p, respectively; it takes more time cost when analyzing videos with higher resolution.

Fig. 20: Latency breakdown among components.

Executing three pipelines, *i.e.*, SR (~40%), inference (~30%), and reuse (~20%), takes up most of the latency, while DRL-based scheduling and feature extraction occupy only 5% by leveraging parallel processing on CPU and GPU for edge and feature map computation. SR pipeline ① is time-consuming. Although only 6% of frames are assigned to execute SR, it still takes nearly half the time cost because enhancing a frame via SR takes 98 to 210 ms, along with the resolution increment. Moreover, 11% of frames in pipeline ① and ② executes inference also takes non-ignorable (27% - 36%) latency as inferring a frame takes 65 to 86 ms. The time cost per frame in the reuse pipeline is small, similar to 5.8 to 8.3 ms decoding time, but their total latency is still considerable, which varies from 18% to 20%, because more than 85% of frames belong to this pipeline. Compared with other components, the lightweight DRL model incurs only 5 to 10 ms inference time, occupying extremely small time proportion.

We evaluate the computational cost of our proposed system using NVIDIA Nsight [57]. We find that the GPU memory usage varied between 3-4 GB at different resolutions, and achieved close to 100% GPU utilization for 40%-80% of the time.

Fig. 21: Comparison of different schemes for the scheduler in AccDecoder. DRL is better than KNN, and A3C achieves better learning performance than the others.

AccDecoder schedulers. We evaluated the performance of different algorithms implementing the scheduler of AccDecoder, including DRL-based schemes and KNN. Fig. 21 illustrates the cumulative rewards of the video with the training of DRL-based schemes. We choose three well-known DRL schemes for training, which are A3C [47], Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) [58], and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [59]. Through empirical exploration, we find A3C can receive a

satisfactory and stable cumulative reward, which is about 11.42% higher than the cumulative reward received by KNN and PPO. The cumulative rewards of A3C and SAC are higher after convergence because SAC introduces maximum entropy and A3C introduces an advantage function to improve learning efficiency. Furthermore, A3C performs better than SAC in the stability after converging (*i.e.*, the intervals of rewards). Therefore, we choose A3C for the training of the scheduler in AccDecoder.

Fig. 22: AccDecoder vs. baselines in terms of the speed of analytics and inference accuracy on various video datasets (in parentheses) and different DNN models.

C. AccDecoder vs. Existing VAPs

AccDecoder vs. baselines. In this experiment, we run AccDecoder and baselines with different DNNs (YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN with Resnet50) under various types of videos (*i.e.*, highways and crossroads). Fig. 22 plots the results in terms of speed (fps) and accuracy (F1-score). Comparing the performance distribution, AccDecoder consistently ranks first in terms of accuracy, which leads 6-38% higher F1-score than state-of-the-art solutions. This advantage originates from the DRL-based scheduler’s fine-grained pipeline assignment and SR’s accuracy improvement. AWStream and DDS do not offer that bad accuracy as they adjust the video encoding config-

uration on the camera to offer good quality when possible, while Reducto and Glimpse only execute frame filtering to speed up without increasing accuracy. AccDecoder achieves around 35fps, reaching the real-time requirement; furthermore, it can obtain higher speed provided the DRL scheduler sets the hyper-parameter in the penalty function as the corresponding value. Compared with baselines, AccDecoder gets 20-80% lower end-to-end latency except for Reducto. Glimpse and DDS achieve only single-digit frame rates because they leverage the feedback from the server/edge to adjust the camera’s frame filtering and retransmission mechanism, respectively. AWStream provides better speed but is lower than AccDecoder as it calculates the accumulated analytics results and then adjusts camera configuration. Note that although Reducto can beat AccDecoder in terms of speed, it trades this by huge accuracy reduction (*i.e.*, 24%-31%).

Fig. 23: Applying AccDecoder on the baselines. AccDecoder achieves 6-21% higher inference accuracy without compromising much speed of analytics (even increasing some) than existing video decoder.

AccDecoder applied on baselines. As a decoder, AccDecoder can be deployed on existing VAPs by replacing their original video decoder. In this experiment, we plug AccDecoder into DDS, Reducto, and AWStream with minor modifications and plot the results in Fig. 23. In incremental-transmission DDS, the camera iteratively transmits the informative portion in the video according to the feedback from the server. In order to plug AccDecoder, we modify DDS by canceling its incremental-round transmission. By doing so, DDS obtains 7.5 \times speed up, achieving 24fps; compared with the first-round video, with AccDecoder’s image enhancement, F1-score improves up to 19%. Reducto filters similar frames according to content similarity on the camera and then delivers the remaining frames to the server for inference; to the filtered frames, they directly reuse the results of the last inference frame. AccDecoder optimizes Reducto first by using MV to move the bounding boxes in the inference frames onto filtered ones and second by improving accuracy via SR. By such modification, AccDecoder brings a 20% improvement in accuracy and a small latency increment. Like Reducto, AWStream also benefits from the AccDecoder’s multiplexing mechanism, improving about 5% accuracy and 4x speed. However, AWStream sets various configurations according to the previous inference results, while the current AccDecoder

cannot handle various video-quality environments. Aiming to this, we propose AccDecoder+ and present the experiment results in Sec. VI-E. Notably, AccDecoder cannot be applied on Glimpse as its communication between the camera and server is image by image. There does not exist a video encoder or decoder in Glimpse; thus, no bit stream information can be leveraged. In summary, AccDecoder brings the benefits of SR to various pipelines while achieving a good balance of accuracy and latency.

Fig. 24: Performance of AccDecoder under multi-stream environment.

D. Scalability of AccDecoder and AccDecoder+

The confirmatory experiment in the multi-streams (270p) scenario verifies the scalability of AccDecoder and AccDecoder+. In the scenario we designed, both solutions performed similarly, and this section only presents the experimental results of AccDecoder. Incorporating G_i into the DRL state and retraining the two agents, observing their performance on the test set, as shown in Fig. 24. AccDecoder maintains the real-time processing of both two streams ($fps \geq 30$) without accuracy decrement. The average F1-score keeps within the range of 60 - 85%. Due to the current high computational cost of EDSR, AccDecoder cannot support a larger number of video streams or higher resolutions. In future work, we will consider using inference acceleration techniques such as model compiler [60], [61] adaptive batch [62], [63] to reduce the computational overhead of SR and improve the resource utility. This will enable the support of more video streams with higher quality and promote greater scalability.

E. Performance of AccDecoder+

Fig. 25 depicts the performance comparison of AccDecoder+ and AccDecoder for videos in different resolutions, *i.e.*, 270p, 360p, and 540p. AccDecoder+ has a better performance than AccDecoder. The reason is that AccDecoder+ can offer adaptive frame assignment tackling different quality of videos via considering chunks' resolution in scheduling. More specifically, the scheduler in AccDecoder+ selects more frames to do SR for lower-resolution chunks because of the less time cost and more accuracy improvement. In contrast, AccDecoder

Fig. 25: Performance comparison of AccDecoder and AccDecoder+ for different resolution.

(a) Performance on the 270p videos (b) Performance on the 360p videos

Fig. 26: AccDecoder+ vs. AccDecoder in terms of the speed of analytics and inference accuracy.

can only work well in some specific resolutions, such as 540P in Fig. 25, because it is resolution-agnostic and cannot adapt scheduling to the quality of chunks. When breaking reward into fps and F1-score (see Fig. 26), AccDecoder+ trades around 4fps for around 0.4 accuracy improvement. AccDecoder+ can still offer a speed of more than 30fps, which meets the requirement without any reward penalty. Thus, it can improve the overall rewards. In summary, AccDecoder+ achieves better versatility in the quality of videos than AccDecoder while maintaining a better balance between accuracy and latency.

VII. RELATED WORK

Video analytics pipeline. Mainstream video analytics pipelines concentrate on two goals: bandwidth saving and inference accuracy increment. For bandwidth saving, first, since the camera can access raw video, they can use their own compute power for analytics [24], [43], [64], [65]; or they can be guided by cloud's feedback [5], [10], [26], [66] to discard frames containing worthless information (from temporal dimension), thus saving bandwidth as these frames won't be delivered to the cloud. Second, in video streaming system, information of interest (*e.g.*, target objects) are sparsely distributed in each frame, streaming only the region of interest (from spatial dimension) [35], [67], [68] can also save bandwidth. For inference accuracy increment, inspired by the success of image enhancement in video streaming for QoE [12], [31]–[33], [69], [36], researchers try to use image enhancement for machine-centric video analytics [11], [15],

[34]. [15] leverages SR to enhance image details for robotics applications while [11] embeds GAN on Google Glasses to generate facial features for face recognition; their experimental results demonstrate image enhancement can increase inference accuracy. Scaling video analytics also attracts lots of attention from researchers, [70], [71] construct the cross-camera correlation for speeding up VAP configuration setup; while for resource aspect, computing resource management (*e.g.*, GPU [72], [73]) and bandwidth management (*e.g.*, [74], [75]) are also critical in this scenario.

Different from our original version AccDecoder [76] we have implemented, AccDecoder+ has the following advantages: (1) AccDecoder+ significantly improves the generality and scalability of AccDecoder. (2) AccDecoder+ achieves a better trade-off in a multi-stream environment. (3) AccDecoder+ optimizes the MV-based reuse algorithm to support B-frames in H.264. (4) AccDecoder+ discusses more system design details.

Deep reinforcement learning. DRL is well suited to tackle sequential problems requiring longer-term planning using high-dimensional observations, which is the case of dynamic pipeline selection. There is a variety of DRL-based algorithms. Value-based algorithms, *e.g.*, Deep Q-Networks (DQN) [77], use a deep neural network to learn the action-value function. However, they do not support continuous action space like the one in our problem. Policy-based algorithms, *e.g.*, Policy Gradient (PG) [78], explicitly build a representation of a policy. However, evaluating a policy without action-value estimation is typically inefficient and causes high variance. Actor-critic algorithms learn the value function (critic) in addition to the policy (actor) since knowing the value function can assist policy updates, for example, by reducing variance in policy gradients. Many existing approaches are based on actor-critic, for example, PPO [59], A3C [47], and SAC [58]. A3C, an asynchronous algorithm, can enable multiple worker agents to train in parallel, allowing efficient training.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, we propose AccDecoder to eliminate the dependence of existing VAPs on video quality. AccDecoder is a new universal video stream decoder that uses a super-resolution deep neural network to enhance video quality for video analytics. To accelerate analytics, AccDecoder applies DRL for adaptive frame selection to enhance the quality of frames and/or to do DNN-based inference. It is a new way to address the key challenge of accuracy-latency tradeoff in distributed VAPs. We show that AccDecoder can substantially improve state-of-the-art VAPs by speeding up analytics (3-7x) and achieving accuracy improvements (6-21%). Furthermore, we upgrade AccDecoder to AccDecoder+, which is resolution-aware and can adapt scheduling to the quality of chunks, achieving an additional 2-7% accuracy improvement. In future work, we plan to explore DRL for macroblock selection to offer finer-grained scheduling and exploit efficient transfer schemes to improve the high-quality gains transfer.

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